

PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY OF RESIN SOLUTIONS. PART IV. THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SOLVENT POWER, GELATION CAPACITY AND VISCOSITY OF SHELLAC SOLUTIONS IN MIXED SOLVENTS.

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Viscosities of shellac solutions in a mixture of two non-solvents having good solvent power, or of one solvent and another latent solvent have been studied over a wide range of concentration and temperature. The pairs of solvents used are acetone-glycol, methyl acetate-glycol and alcohol-acetone.

Three types of viscosity curves are possible. The position of the minimum in the viscosity curve depends on the temperature and on the concentration of the solute and may vanish above a particular temperature or below a particular concentration. Hence the idea of minimum viscosity signifying maximum solvent power is proved to be fallacious. This is further substantiated by observation of solvent power by the method of precipitation or gelation on cooling. The correlation of the viscosity behaviour with gelation capacity of such systems has been discussed with reference to three-component solubility diagram of such systems.

Indications have been made of a new and rational method of evaluating the solvent power of different solvents for lyophilic solutes.

It has been shown by the author in a previous communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 663) from a study of shellac solutions in a mixture of acetone and water that when a mixture of two non-solvents forms a good solvent, a minimum in the viscosity-solvent composition curves (to be referred to later as simply viscosity curve) does not occur as a general rule but only under some specified circumstances. The composition corresponding to the viscosity minimum, which according to the current idea (*vide* Mellan's "Industrial Solvents", 1939, Ch. V, p. 64), represents an optimum solvent composition, has been demonstrated to depend considerably on the concentration of the resin and in fact, the minimum has been found to totally disappear below some particular concentration of the resin. In the present paper, the study has been extended to other solvent mixtures to acquire a more extensive knowledge about such behaviour. From a simultaneous study of solubility, viscosity and gel-forming capacity of such systems, important conclusions about the occurrence or non-occurrence of the U-shape of the viscosity curves have been arrived at, and a more thorough understanding and correlation of the solubility behaviour and viscosity of such systems have been secured, which

corroborate the previous results and extend them in some important and fundamental aspects.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The experimental arrangement, procedure, method of expressing concentration, etc., are the same as described in the previous communication. Particular mention should be made of the suitability of Hoeppler falling ball viscosimeter for use with such volatile solvents as acetone, etc. over a wide range of temperature even in conjunction with substances like shellac, nitrocellulose etc. which produce sticky solutions. The ethylene-glycol used is of British Drug House manufacture (ordinary quality) which has been fractionally distilled for purification (191-192° at about 70 cm. atmospheric pressure). Kahlbaum's C. P. quality acetone and Merck's absolute alcohol have been directly used. Methyl acetate (Kahlbaum's ordinary quality) has been dried and fractionally distilled before use.

TABLE I.

Solvent (by wt.)	Viscosity (centipoise) at				Solvent (by wt.)	Viscosity (centipoise) at			
	15°.	20°.	25°.	30°		15°	20°	25°.	30°
Glycol:acetone.					Glycol:acetone.				
					Conc. of shellac=25%.				
7'5:92'5	Pptn.	Pptn.	3'379	2'662	7'5:92'5	25'77	13'51	9'067	
10:90	5'512	4'237	3'417	2'847	10:90	21'02	13'20	9'427	
15:85	5'817	4'613	3'763	3'184	12'5:87'5	19'68	13'32	9'687	
20:80	6'362	5'153	4'291	3'654	15:85	19'48	13'85	10'30	
30:70	8'935	7'408	6'102	5'110	20:80	20'73	15'39	11'69	
40:60	13'33	10'95	9'111	7'691	30:70	27'45	20'88	16'20	
					40:60	38'68	29'52	22'82	
					Conc. of shellac=40%.				
10:90	116'2	65'05	33'00	20'66	7'5:92'5	Gel	Gel	224'3	69'47
15:85	88'35	50'09	31'09	21'91	10:90	..	2995'0	149'3	64'71
20:80	81'09	50'63	34'45	24'48	12'5:87'5	..	389'9	120'9	61'69
30:70	89'10	65'26	47'41	33'26	15:85	3632	289'2	114'6	61'48
40:60	126'2	89'86	65'02	47'75	20:80	487'6	209'9	112'3	67'85
					30:70	344'2	208'6	129'6	86'10
					40:60	398'2	259'0	168'8	116'6

Shellac in Glycol-Acetone Mixture.

The solvent used is firstly a mixture of glycol and acetone, both of which individually are non-solvents for shellac but the mixture is an excellent solvent from about 5:95 glycol-acetone to a composition of about 90:10. The study of this system has particular advantage over the acetone-water system already studied in that, here a wide range of solvent compositions (5 to 90% glycol) is available for study as against 5 to 25% water in the previous case; hence, a more detailed nature of the viscosity curves is expected to be manifest by a study of this case. Viscosities have been determined for 25, 35, 40 and 45% shellac in mixtures containing various proportions of glycol and acetone at 15°, 20°, 25° and 30°. The results are summarised in Table I and graphically represented in Figs. 1, 2 and 3.

FIG. 1.

Viscosity curves for shellac in glycol-acetone mixture. (Inset, curves for pure solvent mixture).

The viscosity curves for 45% shellac (Fig. 3) all show sharp minima, the position of the minima varying somewhat with temperature. Thus the minimum at 15° is at 27 glycol: 73 acetone, at 20° is at 23 glycol: 77 acetone, at 25° is at 18 glycol: 82 acetone and at 30° at 14 glycol: 86 acetone, showing a gradual drift of the minimum viscosity towards higher concentration of glycol with lower temperature. This is quite a general trend as can also be observed from the positions of the

FIG. 2.

Viscosity curves for shellac in glycol-acetone mixture.

minima for the set of curves for 40% and 35% shellac (Fig. 2). It is further to be noted that the curves are particularly steep towards the acetone side, the steepness rapidly decreasing with rise of temperature. In fact, for 40% and 35% shellac concentrations, the steepness by the pure acetone side flattens so much with rise of temperature, that the minimum vanishes at 30° giving rise to continuously rising curve. The set of curves at 25% shellac concentration (Fig. 1), however, shows no minimum at any of these temperatures but smoothly rises with glycol concentration just like a pure acetone-glycol mixture. It may be further observed that at the same temperature with increasing concentrations of shellac, the viscosity minimum changes towards a higher concentration of the hydroxylic solvent (glycol). For example, at 20° the viscosity

minima are at 17, 19 and 22% of glycol for 35, 40 and 45% concentrations of shellac respectively. The fact that the position of the minimum changes with concentration of the solute and vanishes below some particular concentration of the solute has been first observed in the previous paper, but that it changes appreciably with temperature and may vanish beyond a definite temperature at a particular concentration of shellac is now well established from the data presented herein.

FIG. 3.

Viscosity curves for 45% shellac in glycol-acetone mixture (curves A, B, C & D); (Inset, gelation curve).

In the previous paper it has been suggested that such viscosity minima exist only above the minimum gelation concentration, *i.e.*, such lowest

concentration of shellac solution as forms gel on cooling instead of separating out in flakes. In an attempt to determine the minimum gelation concentration for such systems, it has been observed that this depends greatly on the composition of the solvent (*i.e.* proportion of glycol to acetone). A determination of the whole gelation curve is therefore indicated to be necessary to arrive at an understanding of the viscosity curves. The complete solubility and gelation data have therefore been determined at 25° and are graphically represented in Fig. 4A. For the experimental method of obtaining solubility and gelation data for such diagram, a later paper of this series is referred to where an extensive study of such data has been made, which has led to some important and interesting conclusions about the solvent-solute relationship for resins. In the graph (Fig. 4A),

FIG. 4.

A. Solubility and gelation curves of shellac in glycol-acetone mixture.

B. Constant viscosity diagram of resins in mixed solvents.

the crossed portions indicate non-homogeneity whereas the lightly shaded portions (parallel broken lines) are homogeneous transparent gels and the blank portions signify clear solutions.

Referring to our viscosity studies at constant shellac concentration for different compositions of the solvent mixture, this corresponds on the triangular diagram to the viscosity change along a line parallel to the side opposite to the shellac corner. It may be observed that the gelation curve is reached earlier at the acetone-rich end than at the glycol-rich end; for example, the first appearance of gelation occurs at about 34% shellac at the acetone-rich end (X) and at about 43% shellac at the glycol-rich end (Y). Hence, proceeding along a line, such as P_1Q_1 (40% shellac), the viscosity will naturally decrease sharply as the proportion of

glycol increases, since we are thereby passing from a typical gel to a free-flowing solution and then it will slowly increase with increase of concentration of the more viscous component, glycol as usual. This well explains the initial steep fall of the observed curves, and the subsequent comparatively slow rise. As the concentration of shellac further increases, the line P_2Q_2 approaches the gelation line at the glycol-rich end also and ultimately meets it at about 43% shellac. Hence, at 45% shellac concentration, both sides of the curve are observed to be very steep producing a typical U the acetone-rich arm of which being steeper due to its much stronger gelation capacity. At 35% shellac concentration, the minimum is seen to exist at 25°, but the curve is rather flat. The explanation for this is that the line P_2Q_2 for 35% shellac just fails to pass through the gelation range, hence the initial high value is due to incipient gelation which evidently cannot produce a steepness in viscosity curve equal to that of actual gelation. It is thus evident why with decrease in concentration of shellac, the minimum shifts towards lower concentration of glycol and at about 35% shellac, the minimum is practically adjacent to the insolubility region. On further lowering of shellac concentration, the minimum merges into the insoluble region and hence the actual curves show no minima. This really happens for 25% and less of shellac, where the experimental curves are smooth continuously rising ones (Fig. 1).

The fact that at constant temperature with increase of shellac concentration, the minimum in the viscosity curve drifts towards higher concentration of glycol, is thus ascribed to a lack of symmetry of the course of the gelation curve. It may hence be safely inferred that the drift of the minimum viscosity towards higher glycol concentration will certainly continue with increase in concentration of shellac and will ultimately approach and, in the limiting case, coincide with a composition corresponding to the point Z, where the gelation curve XZY just touches a parallel line to AC (Fig. 4B).

The already mentioned effect of temperature on the viscosity minimum can also be explained from the three-component diagram. With increase of temperature the gelation curve naturally recedes towards higher concentration of shellac but the point X has been experimentally observed to recede along AX at a more rapid rate than Y along CY, *i.e.* generally speaking, the gelation temperature changes more rapidly with concentration of shellac, as the solvent mixture, gets richer in the hydroxylic component. The approximate gelation line at 30° has also been shown in Fig. 4A as a broken line, somewhat parallel to XZY; of course, the position of the line AX and CY will change to some extent but this has

not been shown in the figure. Hence, with rise of temperature any line, PQ, will tend to cut less gelation area in the acetone-rich side than at the glycol-rich side as a result of which the minimum will tend to get shifted towards a lower concentration of glycol by such rise of temperature. The shift of minimum towards lower concentration of glycol at higher temperature may be so great as to displace it in the insolubility region. The experimental curves will then have no minima and this really happens at 30° for 35% and 40% shellac concentrations where the corresponding curves may be seen to have no minima (Fig. 2).

A very striking fact about the effect of temperature on the viscosity of such lyophilic solutions should be pointed out. From even a casual examination of the graphs, it is apparent that the temperature coefficient of viscosity is higher at the two extremes than at near about the minimum viscosity compositions. In other words, for equal lowering of temperature, the viscosity increases much less at near about the minimum viscosity than at other points. There is, however, no definite composition at which the temperature coefficient of viscosity is least, since this depends to some extent on the temperature as well as on the concentration of the resin.

It is thus clear that the viscosity behaviour of such systems is determined by their solubility and gelation capacity and the once widely upheld idea of an optimum composition of solvent mixture producing solution of lowest viscosity is proved to be inadequate. In a restricted sense, however, the solvent composition corresponding to the point Z, the apex of the gelation curve, may be termed as an optimum solvent mixture. It is to be noted in this connection that though the minimum in the viscosity curves in the temperature and concentration studied generally lie within the limits, 10 glycol : 90 acetone to 30 glycol : 70 acetone, the gelation curve (Fig. 3, inset) shows no minimum in this range but its minimum lies at about 64 glycol : 36 acetone—a solvent composition approximately equal to that of the point Z. This trend of the minimum in the gelation curves to be richer in the more polar component has already been observed in our previous work with acetone-water, but for reasons already stated, the difference is not so prominently perceptible there as to merit a confident mention. This is, however, of real moment and shows the importance of the point Z, as containing the optimum solvent composition at the corresponding temperature. This fact is also true for shellac-glycol methyl acetate and shellac-acetone-alcohol systems and other systems to be referred to later where the viscosity minima always lie wide apart from the gelation minimum and at a much lower proportion of the hydroxylic component.

Shellac in Glycol-Methyl Acetate Mixture.

A mixture of glycol and methyl acetate both of which are individually non-solvents for shellac, has also been studied with reference to the above behaviour. The mixture has good solvent power for shellac from a composition of about 30 to 80% glycol. Viscosity studies have been made with 10, 20, 30, 35, 45 and 50% of shellac solutions in different compositions of this solvent mixture at 30°, 25° and 20°, and a few also at 15°. The results are given in Table II and are graphically represented in Figs. 5, 6 and 7.

TABLE II.

Solvent by wt.)	Viscosity (centipoise) at				Solvent (by wt.)	Viscosity (centipoise) at			
	15°.	20°.	25°.	30°.		15°.	20°.	25°.	30°.
Glycol: methyl acetate.	Conc. of shellac = 10%.				Glycol: methyl acetate.	Conc. of shellac = 20%.			
30 : 70		2'87	2'39	2'10	30 : 70		10'98	8'48	6'876
40 : 60		4'17	3'54	3'07	40 : 60		13'55	11'08	9'226
50 : 50		6'00	5'06	4'36	50 : 50		19'99	16'25	13'35
60 : 40		8'65	7'35	6'28	60 : 40		29'49	23'64	19'25
70 : 30		13'35	10'77	9'38	70 : 30		44'27	35'50	28'33
80 : 20		19'14	15'65	12'99	80 : 20		72'71	56'41	43'90
	Conc. of shellac = 30%.					Conc. of shellac = 35%.			
50 : 50		100'2	74'82	57'19	30 : 70		136'2	90'86	64'45
60 : 40		133'3	99'86	75'09	40 : 60		190'1	127'8	89'78
65 : 35		159'9	118'0	88'84	50 : 50		251'6	171'6	121'6
70 : 30		210'8	152'9	112'9	60 : 40		353'0	246'7	177'9
75 : 25		278'1	196'2	143'0	65 : 35		474'7	327'7	229'2
80 : 20		365'5	259'5	186'8	70 : 30		606'2	416'9	288'7
					80 : 20		974'7	651'3	447'2
	Conc. of shellac = 45%.					Conc. of shellac = 50%.			
30 : 70	1276'0	633'9	365'9	227'0	30 : 70	81'300	4439	1538	714'8
40 : 60	986'5	601'6	379'6	251'5	40 : 60	5'323	2'382	1234	6977
50 : 50	1063'0	676'2	444'5	309'3	50 : 50	5256	2787	1555	915'2
60 : 40	1505'0	966'2	634'8	425'1	60 : 40	6785	3776	2185	1313
70 : 30	2330'0	1477'0	968'5	640'0	80 : 20	15'980	9313	5520	3232
80 : 20	3967'0	2460'0	1569'0	1028'0					

All the curves up to 35% shellac concentration (Fig. 5 and 6) show a continuous rise of viscosity with increase in the proportion of the

FIG. 5.

Viscosity curves for shellac in glycol-acetone mixture.

FIG. 6.

Viscosity curves for shellac in glycol-methyl acetate mixture.

more viscous component, glycol, just like pure glycol-methyl acetate mixture. The first appearance of minimum in the viscosity curve occurs at 45% shellac concentration at 20°, rather distinctly at 15° (Fig. 6). At 50% shellac concentration, the minima are all very well-marked (Fig. 7). The relative change of position of the minima with variation of temperature and concentration of shellac is similar to that noticed in the previous case of glycol-acetone and is likewise very distinctly observable here. There are also other points of resemblance which we omit to refer to as a side comparison of the different graphs easily brings them to light.

FIG. 7.

Viscosity curve for shellac (50% conc.) in glycol-methyl acetate mixture (Inset-gelation curves for 45 and 50% shellac conc.).

It is further to be noted that though the viscosity minima lie at about 40 to 50% glycol, the gelation curves show minima at 66% glycol, which, however, lie at about the same value for 45 and 50%

concentrations of shellac. The precipitation curves for lower concentrations of shellac (experimentally determined for 10 and 20% shellac) also tend to show minima at about the same solvent composition, but the curves are not so smooth since the phase which separates at the precipitation temperature is in some cases liquid and in some cases solvated solid.

FIG. 8.

Viscosity curve for shellac (35% conc.) in acetone-alcohol mixture (Inset for 20% conc. of shellac). Dotted curve represents gelation curve for 55% shellac conc.).

Shellac in Alcohol-Acetone Mixture.

These general considerations appear to be applicable even with a solvent-latent solvent mixture, and mixtures of alcohol and acetone have been studied to test this point. Measurements of viscosity have been made at

25 and 35% shellac concentrations in various compositions of the solvent mixture at 15°, 20°, 25° and 30°. The results are presented in Table III and graphically represented in Fig. 8.

TABLE III.

Solvent (by wt.). Alcohol: acetone.	Viscosity (centipoise) at				Solvent (by wt.). Alcohol: acetone.	Viscosity (centipoise) at			
	15°.	20°.	25°	30°.		15°.	20°.	25°.	30°.
	Conc. of shellac = 20%.					Conc. of shellac = 35%.			
10:90	2.023	1.765	1.541	1.353	5:95	Gel	Gel	17.75	9.978
20:80	2.024	1.799	1.603	1.443	10:90	43.11	19.61	12.34	8.851
40:60	2.427	2.154	1.928	1.722	20:80	17.41	13.20	10.19	8.050
60:40	3.206	2.823	2.496	2.245	60:40	18.98	15.58	12.86	10.66
					80:20	26.01	21.31	17.34	14.28
					100:0	38.40	31.10	25.24	20.50

The gelation or precipitation temperature could not be measured at these shellac concentrations as some of them are inconveniently low (below 60°) and hence the gelation temperatures at 55% shellac concentrations have been plotted as dotted curve in the figure. All the features of the foregoing curves with respect to the effect of temperature and concentration are also manifest here. Thus the curves for 35% shellac all show minima at between 20 and 32% alcohol. The curves at 25° and 30° at 20% concentration of shellac show no minima but are continuously rising ones like that of the pure solvent mixture, whereas the curves for lower temperatures (15° and 20°) tend to show minima at very low concentrations (about 15%) of alcohol. The fact that viscosity minimum drifts towards a lower concentration of the hydroxylic solvent with rising temperature tending to vanish above a certain temperature, is thus too apparent. It may be further pointed out as a basic cause of the viscosity minimum lying in the acetone-rich end, that here also the gelation curve is unsymmetrical, gelation being more favoured at the acetone-rich end than at the alcoholic end. The complete curve has been experimentally determined and will appear at the more appropriate place in a later paper dealing with solvent-solute relationship in resins.

As already pointed out in the previous cases, the viscosity minimum is also here widely separated from the gelation minimum, which is at about 80% alcohol. Since this composition, which gives the minimum

gelation temperature, approximates to that of the point Z (in the three component diagram), we shall henceforth term this composition as the optimum solvent mixture, as the composition of the point Z is not so accurately determinable. This gelation minimum is adopted as the optimum composition instead of the point Z, which is the true optimum solvent composition for experimental convenience only; nevertheless, the point Z, is of fundamental significance. Hence, the true optimum solvent composition may be given the following formal definition. The optimum solvent composition is that mixture which requires the highest concentration of the lyophilic solute at any given temperature to just produce gelation.

One pertinent fact about this optimum composition may now be mentioned. For a mixture containing a good solvent (alcohol) and a semi-solvent (acetone), the optimum composition contains a preponderance of the former. If this is assumed as a basic truth, the determination of optimum composition by this method gives us a rational method of assessing the solvent power for lyophilic solutes, for then we have simply to determine the optimum composition for a mixture of two solvents by this procedure. That quite reasonable values are obtainable by such methods is evident from the calculated values of solvent power for the following solvents for shellac (*vide* Table IV). The second column gives the observed optimum solvent compositions for pairs of solvents, and the fourth column contains calculated values of solvent power for the individual solvents assuming that the optimum solvent composition denotes the ratio of the solvent power of the component solvents. The physical significance of solvent power for non-solvents lies perhaps, in its power of solvation of the lyophilic units present in solution. The proper test, however, of such a method is its ability to yield the same value of the solvent power ratio of two latent solvents by comparison with two different third solvents.

TABLE IV.

Solvent mixture.	Optimum solvent comp.	Solvents.	Solvent power. (Alcohol = 100).
Water : acetone	14 : 86	Alcohol	100
Glycol : acetone	64 : 36	Glycol	44
Glycol : methyl acetate	70 : 30	Acetone	25
Alcohol : acetone	80 : 20	Methyl acetate	19
		Water	4

DISCUSSION.

Perhaps, the optimum solvent compositions with different solvent mixtures may furnish some important indications of the structure of the shellac molecule but due to the unsatisfactory state of our knowledge of molecular adsorption forces and polarity, no definite information is available. The idea of an optimum polarity is of no help as calculations of dipole moments of these mixtures on the assumption of additivity of dipole moments do not yield even nearly uniform values.

It is of great interest and usefulness to draw lines of equal viscosity on such three-component diagrams. Instead of constructing it for any particular case, the general courses of such lines in a typical case have been indicated in the figure (Fig. 4B) as dotted lines. This figure is based on the above-mentioned experimentally observed facts that proceeding along any line towards B (*i.e.* increasing shellac concentration) the viscosity increases almost logarithmically with concentration. But proceeding along a line, parallel to AC, viscosity rises steadily but much less rapidly with increase in proportion of the hydroxylic solvent C up to a certain concentration of shellac and then it shows minima. The thick line is obtained by joining the points of minimum viscosity and it cuts the solubility line at the point K. So, all concentrations, less than this value, do not show minimum viscosity, while above it viscosity curves will have minima. Any line of constant viscosity, which passes below the point K, is continuously increasing its ordinate on the line AC (signifying increase of shellac concentration) as it proceeds from the C-corner to the B-corner. Lines passing above the point K, *i.e.*, cutting the line ZK should, however, necessarily have maxima with respect to the line AC. The curves are self-explanatory and such diagrams should yield the technically very important information of how the viscosity of a varnish varies by dilution with the component solvents.

Such curves are presumably also valid for pyroxylin solutions, with the difference that the points K and X occur at a much lower concentration of nitrocellulose. The constant viscosity method developed during the last few years (Doolittle, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1938, 30, 189; Ware and Teeters, *ibid.*, 1939, 31, 738) which proposes to find out that composition of the solvent mixture, which has the maximum solid content for a given viscosity, evidently yields any point on the line ZK instead of the true optimum composition, Z, the position of this so-called optimum solvent ratio, hence depending on the viscosity chosen for comparison. Doolittle's phase diagram, however, affords data useful to lacquer industry and is certainly

to be regarded as the first rational attempt towards solvent power evaluation. One point about Doolittle's phase diagram, however, is not clear to the author. It is a mathematical truth that in any smooth parabolic type curve, such as the viscosity curves of ours as well as of Doolittle, the point of maximum curvature is certainly the minimum point in the curve, whereas Doolittle has drawn (*vide* his Fig. 19) two straight lines supposed to pass through these minimum curvature points. By doing so, the two lines will meet at a point (*vide* his Fig. 20), which according to him is the optimum composition. Evidently, this point again is not our true optimum composition *Z*, but is a composition of the line *KZ*, which is nearest possible to *Z* with the maximum workable viscosity. In a later paper of this series, now under publication, the author has attempted to present a generalised picture of such viscosity changes, which may help to clarify the situation.

It is now clear that the explanation of viscosity of a resin solution has its root in the gelation capacity of the system and such solutions above the minimum gelation concentration may be regarded in a limited sense as incipient gels. This shows the importance of gelation studies of such systems, work on which are under progress and will constitute a later publication.

We may now summarise the facts we have been able to establish about solutions of shellac in a mixture of two non-solvents. Three types of viscosity curves are possible as described below under (a), (b) and (c) and the effects of temperature and concentration are shortly summarised under (d) and (e) below :—

Type (a).—The viscosity curve is somewhat steeper than that of the pure solvent mixture and shows no minimum, but a continuous increase of viscosity with increase in proportion of the hydroxylic solvent. This generally happens for low concentrations of shellac, which is far off the minimum gelation concentration.

Type (b).—The viscosity curve is characterised by a steep fall followed by a slow rise, somewhat steeper than that of the pure solvent mixture. This tends to take place nearing that concentration of shellac which produces gelation at only one extreme of the solvent compositions.

Type (c).—The viscosity curve is very steep on both sides and so assumes almost a U-shape. This occurs when the concentration of shellac is such as to produce gelation at both extremes of the solvent compositions.

(d) *Effect of Temperature.*—The effect of higher temperature is to displace the minimum to a lower concentration of the hydroxylic solvent

and to tend to flatten the arms of the U of the viscosity curves. If the temperature is sufficiently high, the minima will vanish from the experimental curve and the viscosity curves will be of type (a) above.

(a) *Effect of Concentration.*—With increase of concentration of shellac, the minimum steadily shifts to a higher proportion of the hydroxylic solvent, *i.e.* towards the so-called optimum solvent composition. The arms of the viscosity curves also become steeper.

Before attempting an explanation of the different types of viscosity curves we must first acknowledge the limitations of the existing theoretical developments on viscosity of lyophilic solutions. Recently a number of attempts have been made to modify Einstein's equation for viscosity of a colloidal dispersion to quantitatively include cases of lyophilic solutions with unsymmetrical particles, a resumé of which appears in a recent book (H. Mark, "High Polymers," 1940, II, 294). A very complete and systematic account of the present trend of these theoretical researches on viscosity of liquids, solutions and high polymers can be obtained from three reviews by Barr, Goodeve and Eirich respectively ("Annual Reports on the Progress of Physics", 1936, 3, 19; 1938, 5, 20; 1940, 7, 329); and also in Reports on Viscosity and Plasticity, specially papers by Bungenberg de Jong, First Report, 1939, 2nd Ed., Ch. III, p. 110; Burgers, Second Report, 1938, Ch. I, p. 1, and Jaeger, *ibid.*, 1938, Ch. II, p. 29). These researches seem to have received stimulus from Staudinger's work on viscosity of high molecular weight solutes but they are still in the course of development and so cannot be profitably invoked to our aid. Though no body denies the important role which solvation plays in such solutions, there is yet no reliable, even approximate, method of knowing the extent of solvation and its influence on other properties, such as viscosity, surface tension, etc. of the solution.

For a qualitative picture we may imagine that due to high solvation, a good portion of the solvent gets immobilised resulting in higher viscosity and hence the viscosity curves are of the same shape as that of the pure solvent mixture ('a' curves). How a typical gel of almost infinite viscosity is broken down to a fluid of viscosity of even less than a poise with increase in proportion of one of the solvents is difficult to explain. If gelation is assumed to be due to mutual coalescence of the 'solvation layer' made of hydroxylic solvent, due to their characteristic association tendency the explanation is apparent. A higher proportion of hydroxylic solvent stops this mutual coalescence between the neighbouring 'solvation layers' and so brings about a lowering of viscosity. However, any such theoretical idea

must be highly tentative and so it is evidently of no use to make a detailed examination of the data in this light. But these data in conjunction with the modern developments on lyophilic solutes, particularly high polymers, are able to present a fairly complete and connected qualitative picture of the whole field, which we shall attempt to do in the next part of this investigation, where the results of further similar studies for other lyophilic solutes, like other resins, cellulose derivatives, etc. will be presented.

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